

MEDICAL REHABILITATION FOR PATIENTS WITH CERVICAL CANCER: MODERN APPROACHES AND INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE.

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Abstract. Cervical cancer is one of the most prevalent oncological diseases among women. The primary treatment methods include surgery, radiotherapy, and chemotherapy. These procedures have a significant impact on patients' overall physical and mental well-being, necessitating comprehensive medical rehabilitation. Modern approaches, along with rehabilitation protocols developed based on international experience, contribute to improving patients' physical, psychological, and social adaptation.

Objective. To evaluate the effectiveness of rehabilitation in patients with cervical cancer, specifically when applied after completing combined therapy (chemotherapy + radiotherapy) and during different stages of treatment. The study aimed to assess the role of rehabilitation programs in accelerating the return to a healthy lifestyle and to determine the impact of internationally based approaches on functional activity and quality of life.

Materials and Methods. From 2024 to 2025, 160 patients diagnosed with cervical cancer (cancer colli uteri) were observed for a period of 3 to 6 months at the Samarkand branch of the Republican Specialized Oncology Center. All patients received chemotherapy and radiotherapy following surgery. Of these, 70% had completed full surgical and combined (chemotherapy + radiotherapy) treatment, while 30% were still undergoing post-surgical therapy. The study aimed to determine at which stage rehabilitation is more effective — after completion of combined therapy or during the treatment process. Rehabilitation was carried out according to standard protocols based on international experience. Each patient was assigned an individualized rehabilitation program and was placed under continuous monitoring. The program included

physiotherapy, psychological counseling, dietary plans, physical exercise, and social support. The rehabilitation methods were tailored to each patient based on their age, general condition, stage of disease, and treatment-related complications. Effectiveness was evaluated using the Karnofsky Performance Index and the SF-36 Quality of Life Scale.

Results and Discussion. During the 3-month rehabilitation period, preliminary outcomes of two patient groups were analyzed. Among patients who received rehabilitation after completing combined therapy (chemotherapy + radiotherapy), 50% achieved a Karnofsky Performance Score of 80–100. In the remaining patients, recovery indicators showed minimal change. In contrast, patients who received rehabilitation concurrently with combined therapy demonstrated significantly higher recovery rates. These patients coped better both mentally and physically with chemotherapy and radiotherapy. Overall, rehabilitation contributed to improvement in general condition and functional activity in 82% of patients. Psychological support led to a noticeable reduction in symptoms of depression and anxiety. Multidisciplinary and individualized approaches based on international experience also proved to be effective in the context of Uzbekistan .

Conclusion. Rehabilitation measures for patients with cervical cancer, especially when integrated with combined therapy, significantly improve their functional capacity and quality of life. Individually tailored rehabilitation programs grounded in international experience are also showing positive outcomes in Uzbekistan.

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